

6G-XCEL

HORIZON-JU-RIA

WP3 DMMAI Framework and Implementation

D3.1 DMMAI Framework Design

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Executive Summary

The project “6G Trans-Continental Edge Learning” (6G-XCEL) seeks to develop a framework for decentralized multi-party, multi-network artificial intelligence (DMMAI) in future 6G networks. 6G-XCEL will broadly engage with 6G stakeholders across the EU and the US through EU-US partnership in creating the DMMAI framework.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly recognized as a fundamental pillar for future 6G networks, enabling autonomous, intelligent, and adaptive network operations. Existing research has made significant progress in leveraging AI to optimize network performance; however, current studies largely focus on isolated AI controllers within specific domains, such as Radio Access Networks (RAN) or Core Networks (CN). There is limited research on the coordination and interaction of multiple AI controllers across diverse network environments. Furthermore, edge networks introduce additional complexities such as the diversity of computing platforms, the aggregation of multiple stakeholders, and the constrained and dynamic nature of such networks.

The objective of the DMMAI framework is to close the gap in research and design by enabling the federation of AI-based network controls across network domains and layers. The goal of this deliverable is to describe the proposed architecture of the DMMAI framework. To do that, this report outlines:

- a definition of the framework, along with its objectives,
- the current state of the 6G architecture, and how the DMMAI will sit on it,
- a thorough description of the different parts of the framework,
- a list of security threats that will occur from it, and
- the implementation approach followed by 6G-XCEL team up until M16 of the project

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation / Term	Description
4G	Fourth Generation Wireless Network
5G	Fifth Generation Wireless Network
6G	Sixth Generation Wireless Network
ADR	Abstract Data Repository
AIC	Artificial Intelligence Controller
AOL	Agnostic Orchestration Layer
API	Application Programmable Interface
CN	Core Network
CTI	Cooperative Transport Interface
D	Deliverable
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
DBA	Dynamic Bandwidth Allocation
DMB	Data Management Block
DMMAI	Decentralized Multi-party, Multi-network AI
EBI	Eastbound Interface
GA	Grant Agreement
HAMR	Hardware Acceleration ready AI/ML Models Repository
K8s	Kubernetes
KPIs	Key Performance Indicator(s)
MAM	Models Action Module
MMB	Model Management Block
MR	AI/ML Models Repository
MSIM	Model Security & Integration Module
NBI	Northbound Interface
NDR	Network Data Repository
NF	Network Function
NFV	Network Function Virtualisation
O-RAN	Open Radio Access Network / Open-RAN
PON	Passive Optical Networks
RAN	Radio Access Network
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
SBA	Service Based Architecture
SBI	Southbound Interface

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SDN	Software Defined Networking
SDO	Standards Development Organization
T	Task
WBI	Westbound Interface
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1. Objective

The objective of D3.1 is to describe the design of the DMMAI framework that includes the 5G/6G architecture advancements in a multinet environment (end-to-end), the data abstractions and the data exchange interfaces and the AlaaS functionality and operations.

1.2. Mapping 6G-XCEL's Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map the 6G-XCEL Grant Agreement's commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed as shown in Table 1.

Project GA Component Title	Project GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
T3.1 5G/6G Architecture	The task of designing and developing the DMMAI framework spans from M6 to M30 and is critical for enabling the deployment of the project's 5G/6G architecture across multiple use cases, such as an x/rApp or an SDN controller. It begins with defining a modern, modular, and cloud-based framework deployable in a CNCF-enabled Kubernetes environment, capable of interfacing seamlessly with other project elements such as RICs and orchestrator platforms. This task, also, includes the implementation of the AI Controller Block, considering the different aspects of placement in the other project elements. As a result, the architecture will focus on delivering a lightweight, modular, and flexible solution composed of container-based microservices, ensuring compatibility and integration independent of specific programming languages. Additionally, the task will define clean, secure internal interfaces between microservices as specified in T4.1, and provide well-documented OpenAPI interfaces to enable seamless north-south and east-west communication with other AIC instances, external EU/US testbeds, and third-party tools outlined in T5.4. Validation and iterative refinements will occur throughout the project duration to optimize the architecture's applicability to the targeted use cases.	Section 2 Section 3 Section 4	Section 2, outlines the objectives and placement of the DMMAI framework within the 6G architecture, aligning with the goals of T3.1. Section 3 provides the high-level architecture and microservices-based cloud-native implementation approach necessary for T3.1, including communication interfaces. Section 4 explains the practical approach to implementing the framework components.
T3.2 Multi-network and SDN environment	Task T3.2 spans from M6 to M30 and extends the DMMAI framework and RIC controller functionalities into the optical network domain. Specifically, the task involves developing lightweight SDN controllers with functionalities similar to those of Near-RT and Non-RT RICs, suitable for the optical network control loops. ONOS is chosen as the primary	Section 3 Section 4	Section 3 provides the high-level architecture and microservices-based cloud-native implementation approach required by T3.1, including

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	SDN platform, with Ryu additionally used for research-oriented agent and shim development. A Near-RT control example includes managing optical channel powers along transmission paths through adjustments of wavelength selective switch attenuations and amplifier gains and tilts. Furthermore, an AIC component will be developed to study the DMMAI framework within optical networks. Additionally, the task includes creating a cross-domain radio-optical inter-controller protocol, optimized further in WP4, with optical controllers implemented in the OpenIreland testbed to facilitate experimental validation.		communication interfaces. Section 4 covers the practical implementation aspects necessary for the controllers and protocols described in the task.
T3.3 Data abstraction and curation	This task starts from M6 till M30 and focuses on developing data abstraction and curation tools within the DMMAI framework, tailored specifically for handling various data types relevant to different controllers, their network locations, and the associated network types. Will be build upon WP2 requirements and leverage the MORE project platform to manage compressed extremescale time series data. Key developments will include extending and enhancing the model-based time series management platform, ModelarDB, provided by AAU. Specific efforts will target improvements to ModelarDB for hard real-time stream processing requirements unique to 6G communication networks. Emphasis will be on enabling tighter integration between ModelarDB and sensor-to-wireless access components, advanced compression techniques including joint compression of correlated time series and developing communication-specific data models that currently do not exist in the platform.	Section 3 Section 4	Section 3 provides the high-level architecture and data handling requirements essential for T3.3. Section 4 covers the implementation approach for data handling and how ModelarDB, which is developed as part of T3.3, is used.
T3.4 AlaaS, Third Party Resources and Acceleration	Task T3.4, occurring form M6 to M30, targets zero-touch service management that will enable decentralized multi-network based on sustainable multi-agent intelligence for the 6G edge network. The focus will be on intelligent placement mechanisms embedded in zero-touch services that will detect/anticipate new service requests/network fluctuations in 6G systems. This task will involve adapting MEAO orchestrator that was developed by IMEC to interface with and use the DMMAI framework for RIC AI functions, facilitating AI access to additional third-party resources such as accelerators or AI workflow elements. It will specifically focus on adaptations needed for multi-RAT spectrum management use cases. Additionally, this task includes the development of workflows using the AMD FINN project 121,122, which offers a compilation flow for low precision dataflow	Section 3 Section 4	Sections 3 and 4 (including subsections 3.2, 3.3, 4.1 and 4.2) provide overall architectural and practical implementation approach, necessary for AI management orchestration and acceleration, required by this task.

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	inference engines. The AMD team will design low-latency, real-time, and near-real-time solutions that fulfil 6G performance requirements and will also engage in defining workflows that empower end users and federated architectures to train, learn and deploy their AI models using energy-efficient low-precision datatypes.		
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Table 1: Mapping of 6G-XCEL's output to the deliverable

1.3. Relation with Other Deliverables, Tasks and Milestones

Deliverable D3.1 is closely related to multiple tasks, milestones and deliverables within 6G-XCEL project. The primary connections are as follows:

- **Task 3.1 (5G/6G Architecture):** This is the primary task closely linked to D3.1, as it focuses on defining the DMMAI framework design, ensuring a modular approach and integration among multiple components and technologies. Its outcomes support the architectural sections of this deliverable, specifying requirements and interfaces related to 6G networks.
- **Task 3.3 (Data Abstraction and Curation):** Focuses on data management and curation within the DMMAI framework. Developments under T3.3 inform the data handling sections of this deliverable by providing approaches for data processing and analysis across the use cases.
- **Deliverable 3.2 (DMMAI Framework Implementations and Operation):** D3.2 builds upon the design produced from D3.1, translating it into an operational framework.
- **Deliverable 3.3 (AI Service Orchestration Platform Integration):** D3.4 depends on the architectural outputs of T3.1 and benefits from the data management strategies developed in T3.3, ensuring seamless integration of AI services into the DMMAI framework.
- **Deliverable 4.1 (DMMAI Security Analysis):** D4.1 builds upon the DMMAI architecture defined in D3.1, by analysing potential attack and threats vectors related to data flows and model lifecycles established in the framework.
- **Deliverable 5.2 (Curated Data):** Validates the DMMAI framework defined in D3.1, building on the outcomes of T3.1 and the AI-based resource orchestration mechanisms described in T3.4.
- **Milestone 3.1:** This milestone marks the integration of the DMMAI framework subsystems, ensuring that they are ready and in place to be used in initial trials.

1.4. Document Structure

This document is organised as follows:

- **Section 1:** Introduces the objectives of this deliverable, explaining how it aligns with the project goals and relates to other deliverables or tasks.
- **Section 2:** Defines the objective of the DMMAI framework. Examines the framework's placement in 6G architecture and shows how the framework integrates with other project components.
- **Section 3:** Describes the high-level architecture and core components including the AI Controller, the AI Service Management and Orchestration layer and the Cloud Native approach. Also, it covers Communication Interfaces, Data Handling considerations and Security aspects.
- **Section 4:** Details the practical steps of implementing the framework.
- **Section 5:** Summarizes the key outcomes from the previous sections.

2. Initial DMMAI Framework Design

2.1. Definition of the DMMAI Framework

The Decentralized Multi-party, Multi-network AI (DMMAI) Framework is a comprehensive and adaptable blueprint engineered to seamlessly embed AI and ML technologies into intricate network architectures, spanning all network domains. Its core objective is to cultivate cohesive interaction and unified control across all network components in a decentralized and multi-party manner, thereby establishing a 'multi-network' approach.

Functioning as a foundational structure, the DMMAI framework offers a detailed yet flexible architecture for continuous development and advancements in AI/ML-powered network management. While it describes essential components and functionalities for effective integration, it is intentionally designed to accommodate future technological progress and expansions, ensuring its enduring relevance within the dynamic network landscape, with the ambition of extending its applicability beyond current O-RAN implementations to future 6G networks.

The framework strategically utilizes the O-RAN architecture and its Radio Intelligent Controller (RIC) to investigate control mechanisms for decentralized multi-party applications (xApps/rApps), with the aim of creating a generic and adaptable framework applicable across diverse network domains.

2.2. Objective of the DMMAI Framework

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a technology that during the last years has found great adoption in various fields, an adoption that keeps increasing. Networking and mobile communications is some of the fields that have adopted AI on almost all levels. The change of the mobile core architecture from monolithic to service-based architecture (SBA), an effort that started with fourth-generation mobile networks (4G) but matured with fifth-generation mobile networks (5G) [1], has enabled researchers and developers to experiment with the idea of integrating AI/ML techniques in different parts of the core network. Moreover, other initiatives like Open-RAN (O-RAN) alliance, realised the trend and tried to create an architecture that has a more structured approach towards AI, especially AI-enabled control with Radio Access Network (RAN) intelligent controllers (RICs) [2]. However, both efforts came into 5G as an afterthought, resulting in proprietary implementations, not clearly defined goals, and multiple challenges when it comes to integration with multivendor solutions. Finally, in the transport layer, traditional dedicated fiber fronthaul networks are being reconsidered in favour of Passive Optical Networks (PON) to reduce connectivity costs and support the increased small cell densification required for 5G and beyond. However, the challenge of latency caused by Dynamic Bandwidth Allocation (DBA) remains a significant issue. Concepts like "Cooperative DBA" have been introduced to mitigate this latency by facilitating better coordination between optical and mobile networks. This concept has been further developed and standardized as the "Cooperative Transport Interface (CTI)," which allows for enhanced synchronization between PON and RAN upstream schedulers, resulting in more efficient resource allocation and reduced latency. Despite these advancements, the integration of AI capabilities into the PON has not been fully explored [3].

The Decentralized Multi-party, Multi-network AI (DMMAI) framework aims to address the complexities of integrating AI/ML technologies into network architectures while enabling seamless interaction across all network elements in both radio and optical domains. It is designed to establish a unified multi-network approach.

DMMAI also serves as a foundational blueprint, offering a structured yet adaptable framework for future development and enhancements. While it defines the essential components and functionalities for effective AI/ML integration, it remains flexible to support future expansions and technological advancements, ensuring its continued relevance in the evolving landscape of network technology.

2.3. Role of the DMMAI Framework in the Project

As per objective 1 of the project (O1.2), a major outcome of the 6G-XCEL project will be the design and development of the DMMAI framework for the study of AI-based network controls for 6G. It will be a key tool to provide research insights that will be used to answer how distributed technologies, and native AI will be used in the 6G architecture.

2.4. DMMAI Framework's Placement in 6G Architecture

2.4.1. Overview of 6G SBA Architecture

SBA was introduced in the 4G era but was officially established in the 5G Release standards regarding Core Network (CN) [1] [4]. The shift to this kind of software architecture meant that Network Functions (NFs) would move away from point-to-point communications towards a micro-service like architecture. This new approach is supposed to help the CN be more modular and customizable in order to effectively meet on-demand requirements of the users (i.e. custom slicing) [5].

On top of that, the effort to create service-oriented RAN begun during the 5G. The disaggregation of RAN, allowed RAN functions to split into different physical network units. RAN is mainly split in high- and low-layer protocols (Central Unit (CU) and Distributed Units (DUs)). Another kind of split for RAN is between Control- and User-Plane (CP/UP). These splits allowed to virtualise an increasing amount of RAN NFs. However, due the tight coupling between the RAN NFs and due to 5G architectural constraints, it is made almost impossible for the virtualised RAN components to communicate in a SB way [6].

In 6G networks, an advanced architectural framework will integrate functionalities of both the radio access network (RAN) and core network into a unified set of network functions. This convergence is designed to streamline network architecture and operations, minimize signalling overhead and latency, enhance deployment-specific customization through open interfaces, and align with 6G performance requirements. This framework builds upon the SBA adopted in CNs, where core NFs are structured around a service-oriented paradigm.

Core NFs are going to be interconnected via a service bus, which enables access to their capabilities through representational state transfer (REST)-based interfaces. The service bus supports both request/response and subscribe/notify communication models, ensuring network function decoupling. This decoupling allows independent provisioning and scaling of network functions, significantly enhancing architectural flexibility.

Furthermore, the service-oriented design approach extends to the RAN, facilitating the cloud-native deployment of RAN NFs. This flexibility enables dynamic resource allocation, scalability, and efficient network function orchestration, which are essential for the next-generation mobile network paradigm [5] [6].

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Figure 1 : 6G SBA and DMMAI framework placement in it.

2.4.2. DMMAI Framework as part of the 6G SBA Architecture

DMMAI framework aims to sit along the whole 6G architecture, as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** The original idea of the framework is that it will be able to be deployed alongside network services on any given layer, by using as much as possible the same methods, and provide another way of communication between the different network layers.

2.5. Design Principles and Goals

2.5.1. Service Based Architecture

Service Based Architecture is a software development paradigm that organizes applications as a collection of loosely coupled, reusable services. Each service encapsulates a specific business

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capability and operates independently, enabling seamless interoperability across diverse platforms and programming languages. SBA facilitates modular software design by allowing developers to integrate existing services into different systems or compose multiple independent services to execute complex workflows. This architectural approach enhances software scalability, promotes code reusability, and streamlines system integration, making it a foundational principle for modern distributed computing environments.

The DMMAI framework adopts this paradigm to align with the architectural evolution set forth by 5G and anticipated in 6G networks. By leveraging SBA principles, DMMAI ensures compatibility with emerging network architectures, facilitating flexibility, scalability, and efficient AI-driven operations across multi-network environments.

2.5.2. Cloud-Native Applications

A cloud-native application is architected from the ground up to leverage the elasticity, scalability, and distributed nature of cloud environments. To better understand cloud-native applications, it is useful to contrast them with monolithic applications—traditional software architectures that function as tightly integrated, single-unit systems.

Monolithic applications are typically built with customized operating systems, middleware, and language stacks, where scripts and processes are specifically designed for application build, testing, and deployment. This architecture creates strong dependencies between components, making it increasingly difficult to modify, test, deploy, and scale as the system evolves. While initially simple to develop and deploy, monolithic systems often become complex, rigid, and operationally challenging over time.

In contrast, cloud-native applications are designed to harness the advantages of modern distributed infrastructure, ensuring greater agility, scalability, reliability, and cost efficiency. These applications are typically decomposed into multiple self-contained services, employing key technologies and methodologies such as DevOps, continuous integration/continuous delivery (CI/CD), containers, microservices, and declarative APIs. This modular approach enables independent deployment and scaling of application components, allowing teams to implement updates, resolve issues, and introduce new features seamlessly, without service disruption.

By adopting a cloud-native architecture, DMMAI framework, ensures it is future-proof, aligning with the architectural direction established by 5G and anticipated in 6G. This approach enables efficient AI integration, supports multi-network operations, and fosters continuous evolution in an increasingly decentralised and intelligent networking ecosystem.

2.5.3. North - South Bound Facing Interface

Northbound Interfaces (NBIs) and Southbound Interfaces (SBIs) are distinct classes of Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) or protocols that govern communication between different hierarchical layers within a network architecture.

- An NBI enables communication upwards from network components/functions to higher-level systems (e.g., orchestrators, applications), primarily for data retrieval, status monitoring, and abstracted control requests.
- An SBI facilitates communication downwards from higher-level systems (e.g., controllers, orchestrators) to network elements/functions, mainly for transmitting configuration commands, control instructions, and policies.

These interfaces are essential for the programmability, flexibility, and abstraction required in modern networking approaches like Software-Defined Networking (SDN), Network Function Virtualization

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(NFV), and AI-driven automation. They typically leverage standardized protocols to ensure efficient integration and interoperability across diverse network platforms.

Within the architecture of the Decentralized Multi-party, Multi-network AI (DMMAI) framework, Northbound Interfaces (NBIs) and Southbound Interfaces (SBIs) serve as critical architectural elements. They define the standardized communication pathways necessary for interaction among the diverse components envisioned by DMMAI, including distributed AI agents, data processing functions, orchestration logic, and the underlying network elements across both radio access and optical transport domains.

2.5.4. East - West Bound Facing Interface

The East-Westbound Interface (E/WBI) APIs as a standardized framework that enables interoperability and federation between different Operator Platforms. These interfaces support cross-network collaboration, seamless service delivery, and resource sharing, making them fundamental to next-generation networking paradigms such as multi-domain AI-driven orchestration.

E/WBI play a crucial role in federating functionality, allowing an Application Provider to connect to a single Operator Platform while accessing network capabilities across multiple operators. This ensures service continuity and scalability across different network infrastructures. Additionally, edge node sharing enables operators to distribute computing resources more efficiently, particularly in cases where localized infrastructure may be insufficient. Another key function is cross-operator service access, which facilitates seamless integration between home and visited networks, ensuring uninterrupted service delivery in roaming scenarios. [7] [8]

The DMMAI framework is designed to support AI-driven automation across complex, multi-operator environments, making interoperability and real-time data exchange essential. E/WBI align with DMMAI's objectives by enabling multi-network AI orchestration, allowing AI models to dynamically interact with different network domains, share insights, and optimize performance in real time.

By leveraging E/WBI, DMMAI can facilitate federated AI decision-making, where multiple operators collaborate on AI-driven optimizations, such as predictive resource allocation, intelligent traffic routing, and autonomous fault management. The integration of standardized APIs and interfaces ensures that AI-driven network functions can operate efficiently across heterogeneous infrastructures.

These interfaces also support AI-enhanced edge computing, where AI workloads can be dynamically distributed across multiple edge nodes based on demand, improving latency, processing efficiency, and network resilience. As 6G architectures move toward cloud-native, service-based network designs, the combination of E/WBI APIs and AI-driven orchestration in DMMAI ensures a highly adaptable, scalable, and autonomous networking environment.

3. DMMAI Framework Architecture

This section is a functional description of the framework. It aims to provide a well-documented description of the DMMAI's building blocks, but it does not provide an implementation blueprint.

3.1. DMMAI Architecture High-Level Description

Figure 2: DMMAI High-Level Architecture

The DMMAI framework is architected around a modular and composable design philosophy, enabling tailored deployments of AI-driven control across heterogeneous network environments. At its core, the architecture is composed of three primary blocks: *the Data Management Block, the Models Management Block, and the AI Controller Block*. These building blocks are interconnected yet independently operable, making it possible for network operators and developers to select and integrate only the components relevant to their specific network scenario--be it at the edge, core, transport, or access domains.

The *Data Management Block* facilitates the collection, curation, and abstraction of telemetry and contextual data from the underlying network infrastructure. It includes a dedicated Network Data Repository, an Abstract Data Repository, and is protected by a Data Security and Integrity Module. The data pipeline is designed to support both raw telemetry for real-time AI decision-making and pre-processed insights for long-term optimization strategies.

The *Models Management Block* is responsible for handling the lifecycle of AI/ML models used throughout the system. This includes a Model Repository for storing both baseline and hardware-optimized AI/ML models, as well as a Model Actions Module for deploying, updating, or retracting models as needed. Another feature of this block is its Model Security and Integrity Module, ensuring the trustworthiness of models before they are integrated into the network. This separation supports experimentation with federated learning, adaptive models, and accelerates inference at the network edge without compromising security or performance.

The *AI Controller Block*, which will be discussed in detail in Section 3.2, integrates the core intelligence of the framework. It includes capabilities for AI model execution, real-time decision-making, inter-controller communication, and policy enforcement. The modularity of the AI Controller enables flexible deployment and composability, supporting advanced orchestration and learning strategies across domains.

Overall, the modularity and independence of each block allow the DMMAI framework to act as a blueprint--network architects can deploy only those components needed for specific control domains, while ensuring interoperability and coherence through defined interfaces. This flexibility is essential for

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future 6G deployments that demand adaptability, scalability, and resilience in increasingly dynamic and multi-party environments.

3.2. DMMAI Architecture decisions

What led to the final DMMAI architecture is an iterative process. Initially, almost all the framework's modules were packaged together leading to an almost monolithic module. However, moving forward, the DMMAI's blocks were further analysed, leading to a better conceptual grip of the final goal. This led to the decoupling of the modules and to clearly defined framework building blocks.

The catalytic factor on the final design was the "D2.1-Report on 6G-XCEL use case categories and their network and service requirements". D2.1 aimed to define a set of requirements that might underpin a DMMAI framework for its application in reference use cases and testbeds across the EU and US. Additionally, it identifies DMMAI framework requirements for flexible use with various orchestrators.

According to D2.1, the framework should conform to these **functional requirements**:

- i) Resource-aware Edge Learning,
- ii) Model-to-model interaction,
- iii) Security and integrity of AI Models and Edge Learning, and
- iv) Orchestration and Management of Edge Learning Models.

To achieve that, it has also to follow some **non-functional requirements**:

- i) Modular architecture, which can support extensibility and facilitate the integration of new components,
- ii) Support strategies for decentralized control,
- iii) Minimize communication overhead where possible,
- iv) Explore techniques such as quantization and pruning to improve computational efficiency and reduce resource consumption,
- v) The DMMAI framework should prioritize trust, encryption, and secure communication protocols to enhance security, and
- vi) It should align with existing network standards.

To align with the provided requirements, we decided that the controllers should reside near the edge, so that better and more efficient results are achieved. However, that more compute intensive tasks that are at the same time are not time sensitive, should reside in the cloud. This will make the deployments more modular, and straight forward and at the same time it will allow for less intensive requirements by the edge nodes.

3.3. AI Controller Block (AIC)

Figure 3: AI Controller Block

At the heart of the DMMAI framework lies the AI Controller Block, which encapsulates all functional layers necessary to execute intelligent control over network operations. This includes the AI Applications Module (for managing use-case-specific apps), Data Collection, Data Curation, and Enhanced Learning Capabilities for dynamic, context-aware adaptation. The block integrates a central AI Control App, which interacts with AI/ML models and enhanced control logic. Bidirectional communication is supported via North-South (N-S) and East-West (E-W) interfaces, facilitating coordination across hierarchical and peer controller instances. The Policy Supervisor and Conflict Mitigation Module ensures operational harmony when multiple AI agents interact across domains. Importantly, this block also includes its own security components, ensuring that both data and models remain verifiable and tamper-resistant.

The East-West (E-W) and North-South (N-S) communication interfaces are essential for ensuring interoperability across different domains and layers of the network, facilitating scalable and responsive AI-driven operations. The roles and implementation considerations of these interfaces have been previously discussed in Sections 2.5.3 and 2.5.4, where their contributions to cross-controller synchronization and hierarchical control logic were outlined in the context of distributed AI decision-making and multi-agent coordination.

3.3.1. AI Applications Module

The AI Applications Module is a central component within the AI Controller Block that enables the execution and lifecycle management of AI applications for intelligent network control. This module is designed to expose clear and modular interfaces for both data access and control actions, allowing AI developers and network operators to seamlessly retrieve performance measurement data and issue

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control commands across different layers of the network. Through its tight integration with the data curation and data collection subsystems, the module ensures that AI applications can operate on up-to-date, context-rich telemetry with minimal overhead.

In addition to inference, the module supports online training of local AI models, allowing adaptation to dynamic network conditions in near real-time. For more complex learning scenarios, the module also facilitates federated learning by participating in decentralized model training workflows. In this setup, local models are trained across multiple nodes without centralizing data, and only model updates or gradients are exchanged. These collaborative learning processes are coordinated via the East-West (E-W) communication interfaces, which enable direct interaction with other AI controllers and learning agents across the distributed network. This capability is particularly critical in large-scale 6G environments where data locality, privacy, and scalability are paramount. By combining flexible model training with interoperable control and data access interfaces, the AI Applications Module serves as a versatile runtime environment for deploying intelligent, adaptive, and autonomous network services.

3.3.2. Network Data Repository

The Network Data Repository within the AI Controller Block serves as a localized data storage and access layer, tailored to the specific network domain in which the controller is deployed. Unlike the centralized Network Data Repository in the Data Management Block, which aggregates and curates telemetry across the entire network, this local repository is designed for real-time access, inference, and training at the edge or domain-specific level. It collects telemetry, event logs, and performance metrics from nearby network elements and makes them readily available to the AI Applications Module and AI Control App, ensuring low-latency data access for AI-driven decision-making.

These localized repositories are essential for enabling domain-specific intelligence and autonomy, as they provide the data foundation for executing local AI models and supporting online training. Furthermore, they act as intermediaries for data exchange with the centralized Data Management Block.

3.3.3. Policy Supervisor and Conflict Mitigation Module

The Policy Supervisor and Conflict Mitigation Module plays a critical role in ensuring coordinated and reliable operation of multiple AI control applications within the AI Controller Block. This module is responsible for enforcing predefined network policies, such as service-level agreements (SLAs), resource prioritization rules, or slice isolation requirements, by continuously monitoring the behavior of AI applications and intervening when their actions deviate from the expected policy boundaries. It acts as a guardrail for AI decision-making, ensuring that autonomous control remains aligned with operator intent and regulatory constraints.

A key function of this module is to detect and resolve conflicts that may arise when multiple AI applications independently control overlapping resources or pursue competing objectives. For example, in O-RAN deployments, one xApp might aim to optimize user throughput by reallocating radio resources, while another xApp attempts to enforce latency constraints for a URLLC service, leading to conflicting control decisions. Similarly, interference coordination and beamforming applications may issue simultaneous but incompatible commands to the same RU or DU. The Policy Supervisor mitigates these issues by introducing priority rules, arbitration logic, or fallback policies. This ensures that the overall system behaviour remains stable, efficient, and policy-compliant in multi-tenant, multi-service 6G environments.

3.3.4. Data and Model Security and Integrity Module

The Data and Model Security and Integrity Module within the AI Controller Block is a critical safeguard for maintaining the trustworthiness and robustness of AI-driven control in distributed 6G network environments. Deployed locally at different network nodes, this module ensures that both telemetry

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data used for training and inference, as well as the AI/ML models themselves, are authentic, untampered, and compliant with data protection regulations such as GDPR and 3GPP policies.

The module performs continuous integrity checks on telemetry inputs and model artifacts, aiming to detect anomalies or signs of manipulation that could compromise AI decision-making. For instance, if local training data is intentionally skewed to influence the behavior of reinforcement learning agents, the module can flag or quarantine such datasets. Similarly, before deploying or updating a model, the module verifies its cryptographic signature or hash to ensure it originates from a trusted source and has not been altered. This is a necessary step to prevent the injection of neural trojans, counterfeit models, or malicious fine-tuning, which pose significant threats in federated and distributed AI setups.

Beyond technical verification, the module also enforces data anonymization and compliance policies, making sure that sensitive user or network information is properly masked or removed before being used for training or shared across controllers. This is crucial in a multi-party setting, where the threat model includes internal actors, such as compromised network nodes or untrusted AI agents, rather than only external adversaries. By embedding this module into each AI Controller instance, the DMMAI framework strengthens the foundation of trust, accountability, and resilience needed for secure and autonomous AI operations at scale.

3.4. Data Management Block (DMB)

Figure 4: Data Management Block

The Data Management Block (DMB) enables the secure, curated, and interoperable data exchange between heterogeneous network domains and the DMMAI framework's functional components. It acts as the intermediary, responsible for transforming raw data, collected from various AI Controllers (AICs) and network monitoring mechanisms, into high-level, abstracted and semantically enriched datasets optimized for AI/ML training and inference tasks across the framework.

In minimal or centralized deployments, the DMB may exist as a singular, centralised entity that serves the data processing and curation needs of the entire network. However, in larger-scale or distributed deployments, the architecture supports a federated DMB model, where multiple DMB instances are deployed across different network segments. These federated DMBs communicate and exchange data in a synchronised way, that enables low-latency, location-aware data access while it maintains consistency and completeness across the network-wide data fabric.

This federated approach aligns with DMMAI's goals of scalability, resilience, and decentralisation, and ensures that localised intelligence can be realised without compromising access to broader network insights. It also supports the secure sharing of data among multiple administrative domains or infrastructure providers, promoting trust and compliance in multi-party AI scenarios.

3.4.1. Network Data Repository

Network Data repository (NDR) is the entry point of DMB. It is responsible to aggregate the data of all the AICs and telemetry mechanisms that correspond to the specified DMB. The goal of this repository

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is to collect data from all the network elements across core, radio, and transport domains, so that they can be used in unison for curation.

The tool that is going to fulfil the NDR's role should be able to:

- Support multi-source data ingestion. This is important due to the different data sources providing data (RAN, CN, TN, telemetry tools, etc.) and due to the various protocols, that can be used for data collection (e.g. REST APIs, SNMP, MQ messages, etc.)
- Support time-series and event data, as in a network environment there is both a high frequency of data flow regarding variables of the network as well as event data regarding the various states of each component as well as various alerts set-up in the system.
- Structured mechanism to handoff the stored data to the rest of the DMB modules.
- Scalability and resilience, in order to accommodate the high flow and volume of telemetry data.

3.4.2. Data Curation Processes

The data curation processes are responsible to refine, filter, normalise and structure the data stored to the NDR in order to bridge them with the abstract data repository. To effectively achieve their goals, these processes need to execute several important tasks.

First, they need to automatically preprocess the given raw data. This preprocessing should include, but not be confined into, data normalisation and noise reduction to prepare the raw data to become effective datasets. Afterwards there needs to be a data validation and quality assessment process that checks for anomalies and inconsistencies in the data. Another important data processing step is the data transformation into a single structured model (e.g. JSON, YAML, etc.).

Moreover, to create a dataset, an important processing is the data labelling and their semantic annotation. The creation of these metadata give context to the datasets and enables their reusability in different scenarios and networks.

All the above processes should be done in a policy aware manner, as different network domains are facing different challenges, and their data serve different needs.

Finally, scalability and resilience should be taken into consideration, in order to accommodate the high flow and volume of telemetry data.

3.4.3. Data Security and Integrity Module

Data security and Integrity Module (DSIM) could be a part of the data curation processes but due to its importance it is depicted as a separate block. It is responsible to mitigate threats, that are listed in section 3.10.1. Moreover, it is responsible to anonymise the data and make them compliant with GDPR and / or 3GPP data handling policies.

3.4.4. Abstract Data Repository

Abstract Data Repository (ADR) needs to bridge the gap between curated data and higher AI/ML processes. As the ML model repository of a multi-domain framework, it needs to store datasets that are useful across different AI components that reside in different domains of the network. Moreover, as in the case of NDR, it would be useful needs to support federated data management due to the federated nature of DMBs.

In addition to the above, ADR should support enhanced metadata-enhanced discovery and indexing of the stored datasets, to improve its performance and enable further postprocessing processes on the already stored datasets. It should also be able to transform datasets into ML-friendly formats, in order to enable a more seamless bridging with the higher ML processes. All the collected datasets should be also audited by the DSIM.

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Finally, to provide the datasets to the other parts of the architecture, it should have a data exposure interface (e.g. a structured API). This will allow the training modules use the collected and structured data effectively for their purposes, as well as it will allow feedback loops from the AIC and the AI/ML processes to annotate abstract datasets with model performance outcomes.

3.5. Models Management Block (MMB)

Figure 5: Models Management Block

The Models Management Block (MMB) is a core functional unit within the DMMAI framework, responsible for the lifecycle management, storage, optimisation, and security of AI/ML models used throughout the system. It bridges the gap between the DMB and the AIC as it takes the structured data that DMB provides and turns them into AI/ML models that are ready to be used by the intelligent control applications that are deployed throughout the network. The MMB is consisted by 3 components: i) the Model Actions Module, ii) the Model Security and Integrity Module, iii) and the AI/ML Models Repository.

3.5.1. Model Actions Module

Models Actions Module is tasked to manage the full lifecycle of an AI/ML model into the scope of DMMAI framework. It stands between the DMB and the models repository, so that it can both create and store new models and manage already existing ones. Moreover, it should perform model validation and testing of the models before they are permanently stored and before they are deployed.

It should also integrate with the Model Security and Integrity Module (MSIM) in order to audit the newly created models and ensure the model integrity over time.

3.5.2. Model Security and Integrity Module

Model Security and Integrity Module could be a part of the model actions module but due to its importance it is depicted as a separate block. It is responsible to mitigate threats, that are listed in section 3.10.1.

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3.5.3. Models Repository

The model repository should be a component for storing, managing and distributing AI/ML models. In order to effectively achieve that, it ought to support efficient model storage for all different kinds of models (e.g. PyTorch, Tensorflow, x). Moreover, it has to be able to associate metadata to the models for more efficient grouping and querying. Finally, the models repository needs to maintain a compatibility layer with hardware, to enable seamless hardware acceleration to the subset of its models that support it.

3.6. Intent Controller Block (ICB)

An intent is a high-level declaration of *what* the network should achieve (e.g., "optimize throughput" or "reduce power") without providing the technical instructions on how to achieve it. AI frameworks generate abstract intents to guide network behavior.

The Intent Controller Block (ICB) acts as a translation layer between high-level AI frameworks and the underlying infrastructure. This bridges the gap between the AI framework generated abstract intents, and the logic to execute these actions on specific systems.

The ICB fills this gap by converting these intents into low-level, controller-specific commands. It is designed as a lightweight translator rather than a complex logic module, utilising static conversion to bridge the AI with diverse Radio and Transport APIs. By functioning as a translator, the ICB abstracts infrastructure complexity, ensuring that AI models remain robust and agnostic to the specific vendor implementation.

In order to better explain the concept, an example is presented. If an AI framework requests an energy-saving measure (e.g., powering down a base station), the ICB translates this intent, based on the environment:

- **O-RAN:** Converts to specific O-RAN E2 commands via the RIC.
- **Non-O-RAN:** Converts to vendor-specific commands for the RAN Element Management System (EMS).
- **Transport:** Converts to equipment-specific vendor commands.

By leveraging the translations provided by the ICB, new models can be easily integrated in the framework, and will keep the framework's functionality intact and similarly, new vendor specific infrastructure can be added to the ICB's logic and allow to be controlled by already existing models. Implementation is relatively straightforward. The ICB interfaces with the DMMAI framework on one side and the infrastructure protocols (O-RAN, IETF, or proprietary APIs) on the other, performing strictly protocol-to-protocol translation. To illustrate a specific O-RAN deployment scenario (developed as part of the initial work in WP5), the ICB is implemented as the core service of an x/rApp wrapper that encapsulates the DMMAI framework.

In this architecture, the DMMAI framework focuses exclusively on the AI lifecycle, handling training, inference, and model Lifecycle Management (LCM). When the underlying AI models conclude on a new goal, the intent is transmitted to the x/rApp wrapper that acts as the ICB. Upon receiving this decision, the ICB translates it into the necessary low-level O-RAN E2 commands for execution. In this way, the ICB is aware of the underlying resources and their configuration specifics, and allows for the DMMAI framework to stay decoupled from the physical topology.

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Figure 6: ICB in an O-RAN xApp environment

3.7. AI Service Management and Orchestration

Figure 7: DMMAI Orchestrator Agnostic Design

A key aspect of the DMMAI framework is its agnosticism towards any specific service management or orchestration system. At the core of this approach is the "Agnostic Orchestration Layer" (AOL) that sits between the DMMAI internal components and any external orchestration systems.

The AOL will act as a translator and mediator between DMMAI and any external orchestrator. It translates high-level intents, policies, and service requests into direct actions that will be undertaken by the AICs.

It shall be modular and able to communicate with the various orchestrators that exist in the different network planes and extensible to allow further integrations with new tools that may come up. To meet this requirement, it needs to implement standardised interfaces (e.g. TM Forum Open APIs, CAMARA Operator APIs, ETSI NFV MANO APIs, etc) to get aligned with existing orchestrators and provide a well documented model for its payloads.

Moreover, to facilitate the abstraction of the operations that can be done by the DMMAI, it might support a service and/or a resource catalog. In this case, each service and/or resource listed in the catalog, will

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be mapped to automated operations. This can be a first step towards an intent-based approach for the management and the orchestration of the network.

Finally, the AOL has to integrate mechanisms that enable the operations on AI/ML applications, such as training, model selection, etc.

3.8. Cloud Native Approach

As 6G architecture is developed, it becomes clear that most parts of the network are designed in a cloud native architecture. In order to be aligned with this, the DMMAI framework is also designed as a cloud native architecture. The purpose of this, is to allow the parts of DMMAI to be highly scalable, resilient, modular and easily automated. Moreover, cloud native design allows the development of homogenous deployment techniques among decentralised, heterogenous environments, like the different network planes.

DMMAI will be using a microservice based architecture, where the different blocks and modules will be implemented by different microservices. The services will communicate between them via either well defined API endpoints or via a message queue. The microservices are going to be containerised, to allow the orchestration through tools like Kubernetes or OpenShift.

Moreover, DMMAI needs to support a distributed deployment. The framework supports operations like data curation and model training that happen over multiple administrative and physical domains that also might span across large geographic areas.

Finally, through integration with Network Orchestration Systems, DMMAI needs to dynamically scale services or relocate workloads based on real-time network conditions, policy constraints, or resource availability, an essential feature for supporting mobile and disaggregated 6G infrastructures.

3.9. Spanning the DMMAI Framework beyond O-RAN

The DMMAI framework has already been applied beyond the traditional O-RAN boundaries in the implementation work carried out for two OFC demos in 2024 and 2025, where it functions not only as an AI-driven control layer but also as a flexible and generic controller framework that accelerates the deployment of cross-domain experiments. In this context, the DMMAI inter-controller communication interfaces have been used to synchronise the schedulers across the RAN and PON domains, enabling coordinated decisions between the two layers without the need to re-engineer the underlying testbed tooling. This demonstrates that the framework delivers value even before complex AI logic is added, acting as a unifying control substrate that allows rapid integration, testing, and orchestration of heterogeneous network components.

Beyond the O-RAN ecosystem, the DMMAI framework is designed to operate across the full end-to-end network, extending intelligent control into the transport and optical domains while keeping a coherent control logic across layers. A representative example comes from the work carried out on the interaction between the RAN and the PON transport network, where an AI controller in the radio domain performs traffic steering based on real-time channel conditions, while simultaneously exchanging information with an AI-enabled PON controller. Through this cross-domain exchange, the RAN controller can incorporate transport-level capacity constraints or expected congestion into its steering decisions, ensuring that users are not moved to cells whose upstream paths are temporarily capacity-limited. In parallel, the PON controller optimises wavelength assignment on a multi-wavelength OLT by taking into account both current optical load and the anticipated traffic distribution resulting from upcoming RAN steering actions. This dynamic and bidirectional alignment between radio and optical domains illustrates how DMMAI enables coordinated optimisation across the full end-to-end path, moving beyond pointwise O-RAN control and supporting a holistic multi-network view that is required in future 6G systems.

These developments are being implemented as part of Use Case 1, where the coordinated RAN-PON control loop serves as a concrete demonstration of how the DMMAI framework supports multi-domain

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operation, ensures consistent decision-making across heterogeneous technologies, and provides a foundation for extending the framework towards additional network domains in the later phases of the project.

3.10. Overview of Security Aspects in DMMAI

The integration of advanced Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) techniques into network operations substantially boosts operational efficiency and automation; however, this simultaneously creates intricate new security challenges. [9] Despite their advantages, AI/ML models remain vulnerable to diverse threat scenarios, including adversarial attacks, data poisoning incidents, and unauthorized alterations of model parameters, particularly within decentralized, distributed systems such as DMMAI. [10]

The collaborative nature of DMMAI, the reliance on shared data repositories and distributed computational resources expands potential attack surfaces. Vulnerabilities within data pipelines, inference mechanisms, or communication interfaces could critically undermine system integrity, availability, and confidentiality [11]. All these compromises could potentially propagate failures across interconnected domains resulting in severe security incidents. [12]

Incorporating AI-based decisions into real-time (Near RT-RIC) and non-real-time (Non RT-RIC) RAN Intelligent Controllers significantly broadens the vulnerability surface. The inherent complexity and distributed control environment necessitate comprehensive security strategies which will protect individual AI modules and guarantee secure interactions among the diverse radio and optical network layers. [13]

In order to secure DMMAI a proactive & integrated approach will be adopted to mitigate threats across multiple network domains and ensure robust inter-domain interactions. This section provides a preliminary overview of the DMMAI security framework. A comprehensive security analysis, encompassing detailed threat modeling and advanced mitigation strategies, will be presented in D4.1 - DMMAI Security Analysis.

In the context of DMMAI framework, the foundational security principles align with the CIA Triad - Confidentiality, Integrity and Availability:

- **Confidentiality**
Confidentiality ensures that sensitive data & information can be accessed only by authorized entities, safeguarding privacy. Considering the distributed nature of the AI and ML models used for network control and optimization it is vital to enforce stringent data access policies and prevent unauthorized disclosure. DMMAI involves robust mechanisms designed to restrict unauthorized access to sensitive data, preserving user privacy, proprietary network information, and operational intelligence.
- **Integrity**
Integrity refers to the preservation of accuracy, reliability, and internal consistency of data and AI models throughout the DMMAI ecosystem. Protecting data and systems from unauthorized alterations or manipulations guarantees accuracy, consistency, and reliability. The operational effectiveness of AI models significantly depends on the integrity of training and inference data. Data poisoning or adversarial attacks on model inputs can lead to incorrect decision-making, model degradation, and ultimately systemic failures. Therefore, robust mechanisms for ensuring data and model integrity are essential to maintain operational trustworthiness across decentralized AI-controlled domains [11] [14].
- **Availability**
Availability ensures the continuous and reliable access to critical services, resources and network functionalities within the DMMAI framework. Disruptions in availability—such as those induced by distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks, resource exhaustion, or malicious manipulation of inference engines—can have severe impacts, particularly on critical use case [12] [15]

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To safeguard against these threats, DMMAI prioritizes resilient architectural designs, redundant control mechanisms, and real-time monitoring systems capable of rapidly detecting and responding to threats, ensuring uninterrupted and efficient operation of network services.

Incorporating the CIA principles within the DMMAI framework thus provides a structured and comprehensive security approach, critical to the dependable operation and widespread adoption of AI-integrated 6G network technologies.

To ensure full-stack protection, we identify and categorize the following threat types and align them with their corresponding architectural components of the DMMAI framework in Table 2.

Figure 8: Security Threats in DMMAI Architecture

	Threat Category	DMMAI Component	Security Attribute (CIA Triad)
1	AI Model Security (Evasion Attacks, Model Poisoning, Model Extraction & Inversion)	Near RT-RIC, Non RT-RIC, AI Controller (AIC), AI Service Management & Orchestration	Integrity, Confidentiality
2	Data Integrity & Secure Processing (Data Poisoning, Privacy Breaches)	Raw Data Repository, Abstract Data Repository	Integrity, Confidentiality
3	AI Service & API Security (Unsecured API Access, Insider Threats & API Misuse)	TMF APIs, SDN Controllers, Controller Intent/Context Translator	Integrity, Confidentiality
4	Network & Infrastructure Threats (AI-powered SDN Threats, RIC Exploits)	Transport SDN & Network OS, Near RT-RIC, Non RT-RIC	Availability, Integrity
5	Supply Chain & AI Model Lifecycle Security (Backdoor Attacks in AI Models, Compromised AI Model Updates)	AI Model Repository, AI Controller (AIC)	Integrity, Confidentiality
6	AI-driven Threat Intelligence & Monitoring (Undetected AI Model Drift, Lack of AI-based Security Monitoring)	Transport SDN, Network OS, Near RT-RIC, Non RT-RIC	Availability, Integrity

Table 2: Security Threats in DMMAI Architecture

3.10.1. Threat Overview Based on DMMAI Architecture

1. AI Model Security

Components: Near RT-RIC, Non RT-RIC, AI Controller (AIC), AI Service Management & Orchestration

AI models deployed in these components are vulnerable to evasion attacks, poisoning, and inversion. Attackers could manipulate input data streams or inject faulty training data to influence model behaviour. The distributed nature of model execution increases the complexity of detecting and isolating compromised nodes. [16]

2. Data Integrity and Secure Processing

Components: Network Data Repository (Raw), Abstract Data Repository (Processed)

Data repositories, critical for AI training and inference, can be vulnerable to subtle data poisoning attacks. Such attacks involve introducing seemingly benign data patterns that eventually trigger malicious behaviours. The key security challenge here is the trustworthy validation of data integrity, as deceptive alterations are notoriously difficult to detect without sophisticated analytical tools. [14]

3. AI Service and API Security

Components: TMF APIs, SDN Controllers, Controller Intent/Context Translator

Unsecured API endpoints represent critical security vulnerabilities. Weak or absent authentication and encryption facilitate unauthorized modifications, potentially compromising AI service orchestration and inter-domain control processes. [17]

4. Network and Infrastructure Threats

Components: Transport SDN, Network OS, Near RT-RIC, Non RT-RIC

AI-driven network infrastructures, including SDN controllers and RICs, are prime targets for sophisticated attacks. Exploitation of firmware or malicious AI policy insertions could severely disrupt service quality, mobility management, and network slicing. [18]

5. Supply Chain and AI Model Lifecycle Security

Components: AI Model Repository, AI Controller (AIC)

The integrity of AI models throughout their lifecycle—from training and validation to deployment—is essential. Compromised updates or hidden backdoors from third-party models could introduce latent threats, activating under specific circumstances. [19]

6. AI-Driven Threat Intelligence and Monitoring

Components: Transport SDN, Network OS, Near RT-RIC, Non RT-RIC

Continuous AI-driven monitoring is essential for detecting subtle threats like model drift or anomalous behaviors. Lack of robust monitoring tools increases vulnerability to sustained and undetected exploitation [20]

3.10.2. Use Case-Specific Threats in DMMAI

The 6G-XCEL project currently explores two principal use cases that leverage the DMMAI framework: (1) AI-driven spectrum management and (2) AI-based energy efficiency and mobility across heterogeneous networks. This section provides a brief overview of each use case and identifies the associated security threats specific to their operational contexts. A full technical analysis and set of mitigation strategies will be developed in D4.1.

3.10.2.1. AI-Driven Spectrum Management

This use case focuses on dynamic, cooperative spectrum allocation and interference reduction using peer-to-peer and hierarchical AI/ML models across multiple testbeds (OpenIreland, IMEC CityLab, COSMOS). These models optimize spectrum usage and predict traffic under varying real-time conditions.

Use Case-Specific Threats:

- **Spectrum Coordination Manipulation**
AI models coordinating spectrum allocation could be manipulated to unfairly prioritize certain network segments or cause deliberate disruptions (denial-of-spectrum attacks), significantly degrading service quality.
- **Traffic Pattern Injection**
Attackers might deliberately inject false or deceptive traffic patterns to mislead predictive AI models, causing inaccurate spectrum distribution and resource misallocation
- **Inter-node Policy Tampering**
Unauthorized modification of policies during inter-node AI communications can propagate incorrect decisions, causing broader systemic instability within the control plane.

Suggested Mitigations:

- **Distributed cryptographic model attestation**
Ensuring integrity and authenticity of AI models through distributed attestation mechanisms, significantly reducing the risk of tampered or malicious model execution. [21]
- **Secure multi-party computation (SMPC)**
Utilizing cryptographic protocols to ensure privacy and integrity of spectrum allocation models and associated computations among multiple network nodes, thereby preventing unauthorized disclosure or alteration of sensitive operational data. [22]
- **Advanced anomaly detection for spectrum allocation monitoring**
Real-time monitoring and AI-driven anomaly detection systems to swiftly identify and react to abnormal spectrum usage or suspicious AI model behaviours, minimizing potential damages from malicious manipulations. [23]

3.10.2.2. AI-Based Energy Efficiency and Seamless Mobility

Implemented at the University of Patras, this use case leverages AI techniques to minimize energy consumption across heterogeneous network infrastructure while managing seamless mobility between private and public networks. The approach includes integration with legacy network elements via a bespoke translation layer, introducing additional potential vulnerabilities related to legacy protocols and interoperability mechanisms.

Use Case-Specific Threats:

- **Model Update Tampering**
Insecure AI model update procedures could be exploited, introducing hidden backdoors or malicious logic, affecting energy optimization processes and overall network reliability.
- **Mobility Handover Exploits**
Vulnerabilities in AI-driven handover processes could be exploited to cause session interruptions, data breaches, or unauthorized access during transitions between networks.
- **Legacy Integration Layer Vulnerabilities**
Older network components integrated via translation layers could expose obsolete protocols

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and introduce additional security risks, acting as vulnerable points within the network architecture.

Suggested Mitigations:

- **Digitally signed model updates and strict verification procedures**
Implementing cryptographic digital signatures and rigorous validation mechanisms ensures only authenticated and verified model updates are deployed, reducing risks of introducing malicious model alterations. [24]
- **Trusted Execution Environments (TEE) for mobility management security**
Leveraging hardware-based TEEs during AI model training and mobility management operations provides isolated and secure environments, mitigating risks associated with compromised computational resources and unauthorized access. [25]
- **Enhanced API security and rigorous input validation**
Strengthening API defenses with strict authentication, authorization controls, and rigorous validation of all inputs through robust cryptographic and protocol-level protections significantly reduces vulnerabilities exploited through legacy systems and interfaces. [26]

These threat vectors highlight the importance of use-case-specific threat modeling in addition to general architectural protections. Detailed countermeasures, testing strategies, and integration scenarios will be addressed in Deliverable D4.1.

4. Implementation Approach

This section is a description of the initial implementation efforts of the DMMAI framework.

4.1. AI Controller

Figure 9 describes an initial implementation of the generic AIC. Due to the modular nature of the AIC, different implementations can be developed depending on the use-case and the capabilities of the target network node. The implementation presented here is a first version that was published and presented at SIGCOMM 2024 [3] and will be further enhanced with the missing modules as part of the ongoing work in WP5.

Figure 9: Initial AIC implementation

This example implementation includes five key components: two Message Brokers, an AI-Powered Control Engine, a Register, and a Protocol Translation Module. The modular architecture provides the flexibility needed to tailor the design to different network nodes or domains.

Components

Message Brokers: There are two message brokers in this design: *the Local/Node Message Broker* and *the Inter-AI Message Broker*. Both follow a publish-subscribe model, which decouples the producers and consumers of information, making it easier to scale both the AI control applications and the managed network elements. The *Local/Node Message Broker* manages north-south communication, handling interactions between the controller and the managed nodes. Each topic is dedicated to either performance measurements published by nodes or control instructions from the AI control applications. The *Inter-AI Message Broker* enables east-west communication, allowing different AI controllers to exchange information and coordinate decisions.

AI-Powered Control Engine: This component serves as the runtime environment for AI control applications. It handles communication through the message brokers and manages the lifecycle of the AI applications. The control engine also interacts with the Register to obtain information about available performance data and control parameters.

Register: The Register stores metadata about the managed nodes, including available control knobs and performance metrics. It also keeps track of registered AI applications, supporting conflict detection and coordination between controllers.

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Protocol Translation Module: This module ensures interoperability with other AI controllers by handling protocol conversion. It enables east-west communication with external controllers that follow different designs. Direct communication between two instances of this AI controller does not require protocol translation and happens directly between their control engines and Inter-AI Message Brokers.

Node Control Module: Each managed node runs a lightweight Node Control Module that uses publish-subscribe messaging. It publishes the node's performance data and listens for control messages sent to it via the Local/Node Message Broker.

Workflow

Figure 10: AIC Workflow

Figure 10 describes the workflow of node and AI control application registration:

1. Node Registration: When a node is powered on, it registers with the AI controller. It sends a message to the Register, which stores the node's ID, available performance measurements, and control parameters.
2. AI Control Application Registration: After node registration, AI applications can register with the controller. During this step, the AI Control Engine queries the Register to check whether the required metrics and control capabilities are available. If anything is missing, the registration fails. If all needed elements are available, the application is registered, and its details are stored.
3. Operation: Once both nodes and applications are registered, the AI applications can access performance data and control the relevant parameters. This setup allows AI logic to monitor and adapt the network in real time.
4. Decentralized Collaboration: If multiple AI controllers need to coordinate their actions, they can do so through the Inter-AI Message Brokers. This supports distributed intelligence across the network.

4.2. AI Service Manager and Orchestrator

Figure 11: TMF APIs for the DMMAI Orchestrator Agnostic Design

In this section, we describe how to leverage the TM Forum's Open APIs to translate policies, and service requests into direct actions that will be undertaken by the AICs and create a system that can meet the requirements posed in subsection 3.7 AI Service Management and Orchestration. TM Forum's Open APIs are a suite of standardised, REST-based interfaces designed to facilitate interoperability and seamless integration across diverse systems within the telecommunications and digital service provider ecosystems. These APIs are technology-agnostic and cater to various domains [27] [28].

4.2.1. TMF APIs

In this subsection there will be a short description of the APIs that are going to be leveraged by the AOL.

4.2.1.1. TMF633 - Service Catalog Management API

The Service Catalog Management API allows the management of the entire lifecycle of the service catalog elements. It enables service providers to create, retrieve, update, and delete service catalog entities, facilitating efficient service management and orchestration. [29]

The API defines 4 key resources: i) Service Catalog, ii) Service Category, iii) Service Candidate, and iv) Service Specification.

Service Catalog:

Service Catalog represents a collection of available service candidates that can be instantiated into services. Each service catalog can have logical groups, named service categories.

Service Category:

Service Category groups service candidates into logical groups. Each service category can have its own sub-categories.

Service Candidate:

Service Candidate exposes the service specifications to the service catalog. Each service candidate exposes exactly one service specification.

Service Specification:

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Service Specification has the most intricate model of all the resources described in the TMF633. It provides a detailed way to describe a service in an agnostic to the underlying tools manner. A service specification can be standalone, or a bundle of service specifications.

4.2.1.2. TMF638 - Service Inventory Management API

Service Inventory Management API enables service providers to manage the lifecycle of service instances, ensuring accurate tracking and efficient operations.

The API's model of the service is the instantiated service specifications from TMF633 [30].

4.2.1.3. TMF915 - AI Management API

TMF915 AI Management API is designed to standardise the governance and lifecycle management of Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems within telecommunications and digital service environments. [31]

The API defines 4 key resources: i) AI Contract Specification, ii) AI Contract, iii) AI Model Specification, iv) AI Model, and v) AI Contract Violation Specification.

In the context of DMMAI framework emphasis will be given to the AI Model Specification resource and AI Model resource. Similarly to the two previous APIs, TMF915 describes an AI/ML model as a specification and as an instance, allowing to orchestrate it during its lifecycle.

4.2.2. Usage of the TMF APIs by the DMMAI Framework

The Service Catalog Management API will provide the needed abstract description of underlying capabilities of the framework.

Moreover, in TMF915, the AI Model Specification resource is directly related to the Service Specification resource, via a Service Specification Reference. This allows to offer AI Model Specification in an as a Service (AI-Model-asS).

Finally, but most importantly, the TMF APIs are already widely adopted by many industry leaders, and for that reason they keep evolving to meet the ever-growing needs of the industry.

4.3. Data Handling

In this section, we propose an implementation to handle data throughout the DMMAI framework. As shown in Figure 2, multiple parts of the framework architecture require handling data in some capacity. In the AIC, data is collected, curated, and stored in the NDR. The stored data is transferred from potentially multiple AICs to the DMB. In large-scale distributed deployments, data can be transferred from the AICs to multiple federated DMB instances, deployed across different network segments. Once transferred, the data is made available for further data curation in the DMB's internal NDR. The curated datasets are stored in the ADR and made available for use in AI/ML processes.

Due to the modular design of the framework, different implementations can be used, depending on the requirements of the system and the environment in which the system functions. The modularity of the framework also allows for different implementations to be used for different parts of the data handling, such as one implementation in the AIC and an entirely separate implementation in the DMB. However, to provide a simple, consistent, and performant interface to handle data throughout the DMMAI framework, we propose an example implementation that utilizes the model-based relational database management system ModelarDB [32] for all data handling.

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4.3.1. ModelarDB

ModelarDB is an efficient high-performance time-series management system that supports state-of-the-art lossy and lossless compression of high-frequency time-series data and lossless storage of other relational data. Efficient ingestion, compression, and transfer of time-series data is enabled by storing data using multiple different types of models such as constant and linear functions. ModelarDB is therefore ideal for storing data in the DMMAI framework, since both high-frequency time-series data regarding variables of the network and event data regarding the various states of each component can be stored efficiently.

Another reason ModelarDB was chosen for the example implementation is for its compatibility with the scalable distributed architecture that the DMMAI framework is designed for. To support ingesting data in each AIC, curating the data within the AIC, and storing it in the NDR, a lightweight database instance is required in each AIC. This instance also needs to be able to transfer data to the DMB in a scalable and efficient manner to support horizontally scaling the number of AICs. As shown in Figure 12, ModelarDB has built-in support for an edge-cloud architecture, where multiple edge nodes can ingest, compress, and store data. The stored compressed data can then be transferred to centralized ModelarDB cloud instances. This is compatible with the DMMAI framework where an edge node can be deployed in each AIC and data can be transferred to the centralized DMB where it can be accessed in a scalable manner through one or multiple cloud nodes.

Figure 12: Compatibility between ModelarDB architecture and DMMAI framework architecture

It should be noted that a ModelarDB cluster of edge and cloud nodes requires a ModelarDB manager node to manage the nodes in the cluster and facilitate efficient access to the data in the centralized object store. However, in upcoming work, the manager node will be removed from the cluster architecture and will be replaced by a federated architecture that is better aligned with the DMMAI framework.

Each ModelarDB edge node can ingest data using an Apache Arrow Flight API, SQL DML statements, or through the open-source plugin-driven Telegraf agent. Apache Arrow Flight enables ingestion through popular programming languages like Python and Java while Telegraf enables ingestion through most popular protocols such as MQTT and SNMP. Once ingested, data is compressed on the edge and made available for querying through an SQL interface. Since data is compressed on the edge, within the AIC, the data can be both curated efficiently for use inside the AIC and transferred to the DMB using minimal bandwidth. The ModelarDB edge nodes batch the compressed data and then transfer it to the

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centralized object store based on configurable settings, such as maximum batch size and maximum allowed latency.

In the DMB, data in the NDR can be accessed and curated through an SQL interface. Note that ModelarDB edge and cloud nodes function similarly which means that both node types support ingestion, compression, and querying. The main difference between the node types is that ModelarDB edge nodes query data locally while cloud nodes query data from the cloud object store within the DMB. This object store can contain both the data transferred to the NDR and the curated data in the ADR and both can be accessed through the ModelarDB SQL interface. Since ModelarDB supports horizontal scaling by adding more cloud nodes, access to the data in both the NDR and ADR can be scaled based on the requirements of the system.

5. Conclusions

The report provides a description of the DMMAI framework as well as an initial approach on how a proof-of-concept implementation of it will be created.

The description DMMAI's building blocks of, makes apparent that the creation and most importantly the implementation of such a framework is a multidisciplinary effort. The previous generations of mobile networks managed the development of each network domain in a relatively isolated way, leading to non-unified domain specific methods.

The framework's building blocks are designed for uniform deployment and lifecycle management across all network domains. The end-to-end deployment of the framework provides a native way to handle all the network data generated along the various systems involved. Moreover, the DMMAI caters to the AI/ML needs of the network, especially when it comes to the AI/ML flow across the network. The integration of streamlined data curation processes with standardized MLOps practices enhances data utilization within the network. This enables continuous feedback loops between data sources and AI/ML-enhanced applications, leading to more efficient and intelligent network operations.

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